

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS WITH THE HELP OF PODCASTS AND NOTE-TAKING STRATEGY

Erdonova Muattar Rahmonovna

Samarqand davlat universitetining Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti
Xorijiy til va adabiyoti yo‘nalishi 2-bosqich magistranti
e-mail: erdonovamuattar2000@gmail.com

Ungboyeva Dildora Bakhrom qizi

Samarqand davlat universitetining Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti
Xorijiy til va adabiyoti yo‘nalishi 2-bosqich magistranti
e-mail: dildoraungbayeva@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As the English language has become an international language of today's world, the number of individuals who are eager to learn English is rising day by day. In everyday life, most needed skills of the English language are listening and speaking as they are crucial parts of the communication among people. Listening provides the conversation move smoothly – if the listener understands the speech well, it avoids misunderstanding. So, this research has the objective to improve learners' listening comprehension through the use of podcasts with the help of note-taking strategy in EFL classrooms. 30 students from state schools in Uzbekistan were chosen as sample for this research with distribution of 15 in experiment class and 15 in control class. In this research an experimental method was applied. According to the results of questionnaire, learners said that listening to podcasts with the note-taking strategy became really useful tool to improve their listening comprehension as podcasts provide authentic tasks, meaningful and interesting activities to stay motivated.

Keywords: listening comprehension, EFL, authentic materials, podcasts, English, note taking.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НАВЫКОВ СЛУШАНИЯ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ПОДКАСТОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Поскольку английский язык стал международным языком современного мира, число людей, желающих изучать английский язык, растет с каждым днем. В повседневной жизни наиболее необходимыми навыками английского

языка являются аудирование и разговорная речь, поскольку они являются важными частями общения между людьми. Аудирование обеспечивает плавность хода беседы – если слушатель хорошо понимает речь, это позволяет избежать недопонимания. Таким образом, цель этого исследования – улучшить понимание учащихся на слух за счет использования подкастов с помощью стратегии ведения заметок в классах EFL. В качестве выборки для данного исследования были выбраны 30 учащихся государственных школ Узбекистана: 15 в экспериментальном классе и 15 в контрольном классе. В данном исследовании был применен экспериментальный метод. Согласно результатам анкетирования, учащиеся сказали, что прослушивание подкастов с использованием стратегии ведения заметок стало действительно полезным инструментом для улучшения понимания речи на слух, поскольку подкасты предоставляют аутентичные задания, значимые и интересные занятия, позволяющие сохранять мотивацию.

Ключевые слова: понимание на слух, EFL, аутентичные материалы, подкасты, английский язык, note taking.

PODKASTLAR YORDAMIDA TINGLAB TUSHUNISH KO‘NIKMASINI YAXSHILASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ingliz tili bugungi dunyoning xalqaro tiliga aylangani sababli, ingliz tilini o‘rganishga ishtiyoqmandlar soni kundun-kunga ortib bormoqda. Kundalik hayotda ingliz tilining eng zarur ko‘nikmalari tinglash va gapirishdir, chunki ular odamlar o‘rtasidagi muloqotning muhim qismlaridir. Tinglash suhbatning silliq kechishini ta‘minlaydi - agar tinglovchi nutqni yaxshi tushunsa, tushunmovchiliklarning oldi olinadi. Shunday qilib, ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tili xorijiy til sifatida o‘qitiladigan sinflarda note taking strategiyasi yordamida podkastlardan foydalanish orqali o‘quvchilarning tinglab tushunishlarini yaxshilashdan iborat. Tadqiqot uchun namuna sifatida O‘zbekistondagi davlat maktablaridan 30 nafar o‘quvchi tanlab olindi, ularning 15 nafari tajriba sinfida, 15 nafari nazorat sinfida. Ushbu tadqiqotda eksperimental usul qo‘llanildi. So‘rovnoma natijalariga ko‘ra, o‘quvchilar note-taking strategiyasi bilan podkastlarni tinglash ularning tinglashni tushunishlarini yaxshilash uchun haqiqatan ham foydali vositaga aylanganini aytishdi, chunki podkastlar autentik materiallar bo‘lib, qiziqarli va mazmunli kontentga egaligi uchun ham o‘quvchilarda tinglash uchun motivatsiya doimiy saqlanishiga sabab bo‘ladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: tinglab tushunish, EFL, haqiqiy materiallar, podkastlar, ingliz tili, note taking.

INTRODUCTION

Improving listening is a long-term process which must be done with dedication, hard-work as well as proper instructions and methods. Although a number of methods have been developed and applied in our country to develop the ability to academically develop the listening comprehension skills of English language learners, the only test of academic listening comprehension skills is IELTS (International English Language Testing System), test-taking candidates in Uzbekistan show 5.92, that is, 6 points out of 9 on average. If we look at National assessment of foreign language proficiency- Multilevel exam, according to the annual report of Multilevel exam, in listening section test takers show average 49,75 %, not even 50%, which means listening section needs to be improved. Such statistics show that the research conducted on the academic development of listening comprehension skills in our country and the methods that can be used in practice are still insufficient.

Our research is aimed at finding a scientific solution to issues such as the development of methods to develop the listening comprehension skills of B1 level language learners as well as improving their performance in IELTS and MULTILEVEL exams and their practical application. For this, using podcasts from BBC 6 minute English and applying note-taking strategy was chosen.

As far as we know, podcasts are very significant tool to help the language learners to improve their listening skills as well as boosting vocabulary. If the students or learners have a less understanding of vocabulary it will also affect missing information. Hajar, Ibnu, et al. (2020)¹. In addition, The acquisition of vocabulary is arguably the most critical component of successful language learning (McCarten, Jeanne, 2007). Learners can develop their listening comprehension and reach the expected outcome in a short period of time as podcasts provide authentic information and the topics of podcasts range from daily topics to global issues which can help to broaden the learners' horizon at the same time. The development of new technologies has created the opportunities for education to use them in language learning process. The term "Podcast" was derived from two technologies, "iPod", and "Broadcast". Additionally, based on (Rime et al, 2022)² the definition of a podcast is a piece of episodic, downloadable, or streamable, primarily spoken audio content, distributed via the internet, playable anywhere, at any time, produced by anyone who so wishes. Podcasts are authentic materials which mean that learners have no difficulty in listening daily conversations of native speakers and also they can show sufficient results in language

¹ Hajar, I., Rahman, A., Tenriawali, A. Y., & Mangesa, R. (2020). The Influence Of Podcasts In Learning English Vocabulary Of Twelve Grade Students Of Sma Negeri 2 Buru. EXPOSURE: JURNAL PENDIDIKAN BAHASA INGGRIS, 9(2), 235-249

² Rime, J., Pike, C., & Collins, T. (2022). What is a podcast? Considering innovations in podcasting through the six-tensions framework. *Convergence*, 28(5), 1260-1282

exams. In the area of language teaching, particularly listening, Podcasts for example, provide a unique feature of content choice and repository of real-life speaking materials which allow students to study at their own time and pace (Kavaliauskiene, 2008)¹. Regarding to the frequency of its usage, Constantine (2007)² explained the use of Podcasts in the EFL classroom, even at the beginning levels, all foreign language learners can benefit from Podcast by only listening it six minutes a day. Furthermore, a research was conducted by Edirisingha, Rizzi, Nie and Rothwell (2007)³ reported that podcast is successful in supporting students' preparation for assessed work, providing significant advice on portfolio and presentations. In line with this, Rizzi Rothwell, Nie and Edirisingha (2007) and Beheler (2007)⁴ also have proven that Podcasts enhance students' ability in listening.

Based on the above rationale, the use of podcasts in a language classroom is enable students to comprehend content, to enhance their proficiency and to improve their listening comprehension. Unfortunately, in Uzbek teaching context, scarce research existed prior to this study regarding best practices of podcasts and its effectiveness in the context of teaching state school students.

Stanley (2006)⁵ claimed that podcasting can strengthen or reinforce students by giving them chance to create and publish for a real audience and easing and spreading news broadcasts, developing pamphlets, listening to teachers' notes, recording lectures distributed directly to students' MP3 players, recording meeting, lecture, conference notes, supporting student projects and interviews, and offering oral history archiving and on request spreading. Townend (2005)⁶ mentioned that one of podcasts' importance podcasts allow all students to learn. They permit students to access educational materials at any place, while travelling from home to university or work, or doing any activity they want. They can play the recordings at any time which is appropriate to them rather than be restricted to set class times. Inspired by the usefulness and benefits of the Podcast as teaching resources discussed above and have been verified empirically by several experts, this study has been carried out as an effort to investigate whether Podcast can impact state school students'

¹Kavaliauskiene, G. (2008). Podcasting: A tool for improving listening skills. *The Journal of Teaching English with Technology (TEwT)*, 8(4).

² Constantine, P. (2007). Podcasts: another source for listening input. *The Internet TESL Journal*. 13 (1)

³ Edirisingha, P., Rizzi, C., Nie, M., &Rothwell, L. (2007). Podcasting to provide teaching and learning support for an undergraduate module on English language and communication. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 8 (3), 87–107

⁴ Edirisingha, P., Rizzi, C., Nie, M., &Rothwell, L. (2007). Podcasting to provide teaching and learning support for an undergraduate module on English language and communication. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 8(3), 87–107

⁵ Stanley, G. (2006). Podcasting: Audio on the Internet comes of age. *TESL-EJ*, 9(4). Retrieved from <http://www-writing.berkeley.edu:16080/TESL-EJ>

⁶ Townend, N.(2005). Podcasting in higher education. *Viewfinder, Media Online Focus, British Universities Film & Video Council*, 61.

listening comprehension in EFL setting in Uzbekistan as well as exploring students' perception on the use of podcasts in listening classroom.

METHODS

This research uses descriptive and quantitative method in presenting the positive impact of using podcasts to improve listening skill. While listening to podcasts for the first time, note-taking strategy helps them to get the main idea of the audio as well as specific details. Then, for the second time, listening happens with the help of audio scripts. Students can compare their note-taking and audio script which enables them to correct themselves. Finally, it is advised to make the speed of the audio 2 times faster as they can adapt to various audios in fast speed. This consists of 3 steps to follow. The podcasts were provided to 15 students in state schools. The students were given an online questionnaire to know their needs and wishes towards listening as well as podcasts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This experiment was conducted among 15 learners in the experiment group. Before applying the above recommended method, pre-test was taken and their results were recorded. After applying the suggested method, post-test was taken. Then, pre-test and post-test results were compared with each other.

how are podcasts effective for you?

15 ответов

According to results, their performance in listening was much higher than before. Furthermore, according to the results of questionnaire, 93,3% students found the podcasts effective in improving their listening.

my vocabulary enhanced after listening to podcasts

15 ответов

As it is stated above, podcasts also play a vital role in increasing language learners' vocabulary skill. Questionnaire results showed that majority students with 66,7% approved that podcasts helped them to enhance their vocabulary.

podcasts helped to broaden my horizon as they focus on various global issues as well as daily topics

15 ответов

93,3% of the students admitted that podcasts helped to improve not only language skills but also to widen their outlook since podcasts provide global information along with the daily conversations.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the effectiveness of podcasts and note-taking strategy to improve listening and the attitude of language learners to this method. As a conclusion, the use of podcasts was found effective in improving listening skills of English learners. So, it is recommended for teachers as well as any language learners to use podcasts by applying note-taking strategy since it helps not only improve listening

skills but also enhance vocabulary, critical –analytical thinking skills at the same time. Hence, further research and application of this method in language teaching and learning should be done to improve language learners' listening results in language exams.

REFERENCES:

1. Constantine, P. (2007). Podcasts: another source for listening input. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 13 (1)
2. Edirisingha, P., Rizzi, C., Nie, M., & Rothwell, L. (2007). Podcasting to provide teaching and learning support for an undergraduate module on English language and communication. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 8(3), 87–107
3. Hajar, I., Rahman, A., Tenriawali, A. Y., & Mangesa, R. (2020). The Influence Of Podcasts In Learning English Vocabulary Of Twelve Grade Students Of Sma Negeri 2 Buru. *EXPOSURE: JURNAL PENDIDIKAN BAHASA INGGRIS*, 9(2), 235-249
4. Kavaliauskiene, G. (2008). Podcasting: A tool for improving listening skills. *The Journal of Teaching English with Technology (TEwT)*, 8(4)
5. Rime, J., Pike, C., & Collins, T. (2022). What is a podcast? Considering innovations in podcasting through the six-tensions framework. *Convergence*, 28(5), 1260-1282
6. Stanley, G. (2006). Podcasting: Audio on the Internet comes of age. *TESL-EJ*, 9(4). Retrieved from <http://www-writing.berkeley.edu:16080/TESL-EJ>
7. Townend, N.(2005). Podcasting in higher education. *Viewfinder, Media Online Focus*, British Universities Film & Video Council, 61